

FORMATION OF SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE ACTIVITY COMPETENCES IN FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article describes modern education, methods that develop students' creativity, and the role and importance of the law on education in the development of education.

Key words: method, style, technology, pedagogical skill, skill

INTRODUCTION

In our country, the priority of the state policy is to focus on the development of the young generation as a physically and mentally mature person, and the goal of developing an independent, creative and highly spiritual person is definitely included. In the 5 important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the tasks set for the establishment of work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres on the basis of a new system, the implementation of important measures related to the education of young people requires. Also, PF-5712 dated June 17, 2018 "On the State Program "Youth is our future" and August 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" The fact that complex tasks aimed at the education of young people have been expressed in the Decree No. The requirements mentioned in these documents depend on the essence of the innovative changes achieved in the continuing education system and mainly apply to the primary education process. Because at this stage, students are armed with the basics of literacy, numeracy, work skills and elements of personal spirituality. Therefore, the modern education system, its goals and tasks should be compatible with the solution of the problem set before the educational process that serves the development of our country.

These require regular improvement of the creative activity of subjects in the modern education system, in particular, primary school teachers, in accordance with the level of society's development.

In the conditions where the methodical competence of the future elementary school teachers in our country is constantly changing, having studied the advanced foreign experiences, the development of the technology, didactic foundations, pedagogical conditions, content and structure, improvement criteria and degrees of formation, form, method, tools, model, increasing the effectiveness of teaching quality, as well as developing the theoretical and practical basis for the development of methodical competence in future elementary school teachers in a pedagogical higher educational institution is important.

It is important to further improve the experience and skills of teachers in raising the spirituality and professional potential of people, which is the driving force and force of the modernization processes of social life, the main factor of the consistent development of Uzbekistan today and in the future. The teacher lays a huge foundation for the future of our country with the maturity of the students he is teaching and educating today.

Therefore, today's teacher is determined to become a creative person who works tirelessly, is broad-minded in all aspects, can effectively use advanced pedagogical and information technologies, and has high qualities that penetrate deeply into the hearts of young people. .

From this point of view, nowadays, the problem of increasing the teacher's pedagogical skills and creative activity is the demand of the times.

First of all, he is the person responsible for the bright future of students in educational institutions and extracurricular activities.

The success and effectiveness of the teacher's work depends on the conditions that affect the scientific organization of it, the rational organization of work, and the work is always carried out creatively.

Therefore, the teacher who performs the work must first of all rely on his knowledge, his pedagogical skills, when planning his work. Nowadays, in the period of development of information and communication technologies, the organization of the teacher's work on a scientific basis depends on the degree to which the teacher has mastered the achievements of science and technology.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The expected result in the process of teaching students in pedagogic higher education institutions is formed in the form of requirements for mastering the main educational programs presented through general cultural, general professional and professional competencies. The profile (specialty) competence of the future teacher is defined in the state educational standards, which is an important component of the teacher's professional competence. Currently, it is one of the most understudied problems. One of such issues is to determine a competent approach to the development of professional competencies in future primary school teachers and to develop its structural model in accordance with the main provisions of the State Education Standards. In order to determine the professional competence of the future elementary school teacher, we will focus on some studies devoted to the study of this concept. In the studies where professional competence is studied as a pedagogical problem, the characteristics of the teacher are mainly analyzed. V.I. Baydenko described the concept of "professional competence" as follows: - to have the knowledge, skills, qualifications and abilities necessary to work in one's specialty, and at the same time to have the characteristics of autonomy and flexibility in the partial solution of professional problems; - development of cooperation with colleagues in a professional interpersonal environment; - the design structure of the standards, including the performance criterion (quality measure), the field of application, and the required knowledge; - effective use of abilities that allow effective implementation of professional activities according to the requirements of the employer; - an integrated combination of knowledge, characteristics and skills that allow a person to successfully perform work in the modern work environment. Summarizing the above, V.I.Baydenko understands professional competence as the readiness and ability to act in accordance with the requirements of the activity, to independently solve issues and problems, and at the same time to be able to evaluate the results of one's activity, that is, appropriate skills, technical methods.

O.V. According to Hovov, professional competence is not only competence, i.e. professional competence as work experience, skills and knowledge, but also social-communicative and individual abilities that ensure independence in professional activity.

Yu.G. Tatur and V.Ye. The Medvedevs define competence of a future specialist as a desire and ability to demonstrate one's potential (knowledge, skills, experience, personal qualities, etc.) defined as the willingness to use all of one's abilities (knowledge, skills, experience and personal qualities) to be able to work successfully in any field and to be consciously aware of the responsibility for its result. G.A. According to Larionova, the structure of readiness includes a complex of practical knowledge and characteristics that ensure the entry into activity of a person. Preparation for work is complex, consisting of two components, i.e. operational (knowledge and skills) and personal (instructions, work orientation, professional motive characteristics, system of habits and relationships, emotional and volitional functions, professionally important qualities of a person) is a system. Determining what the specialist has competencies, i.e., what method of activity he can master, what he can do, what he is ready for, is called a competent approach. One of the conceptually important ways to manage the quality of training of graduates of a higher educational institution is to implement a competent approach to the modernization of the content of professional education.

The problem of increasing the level of professional competence of a future teacher who has the ability to think freely and actively, to model the educational process, to develop and implement new ideas and technologies of teaching and upbringing, is a modern socio-economic problem. is relevant in the circumstances. The main conditions for the development of professional competence of future teachers are as follows:

- 1) organizational-management (curriculum, schedule of the educational process, drawing up the lesson schedule, development of criteria for determining the level of competence, material and technical support of the educational process);
- 2) educational and methodological (choosing the content of classes, integration of different courses, separation of leading ideas);
- 3) technological (control-evaluation, organization of active forms of education, identification of groups of knowledge included in competence, application of innovative technologies);
- 4) psychological-pedagogical (diagnosis of students' development, stimulation of motivation for teaching, determination of criteria of competence, guidance of students to work in cooperation).

The structure of the future teacher's creative professional competence is determined through his pedagogical skills, and skills (knowledge based on theoretical knowledge and oriented towards solving pedagogical problems) are determined through a set of gradually developing actions.

In the world education science, the leading activity of children is play, and the importance of games in preschool age has been proven in every aspect. The didactic form of games is also of special importance in the practice of primary education.

At the heart of the process of didactic games is the goal of educating students, explaining the secrets of the universe and man, encouraging them to think independently, and forming a person who is on the verge of spiritual collapse. All this increases the creativity of the primary school teacher in his classes. Research on children's games directly states that games are one of the main activities not only of preschool children, but also of elementary school students, and have a positive effect on their personality formation. shows.

Creativity is manifested in the teacher's creativity, which determines the educational content of his professional activity, in the course of his work.

Creativity is a process that creates qualitatively new, original and unrepeatable scientific innovations in the teacher's educational process. Any problem identified in the productive creativity of the teacher can be solved successfully, most of the teachers who are capable of creativity show these aspects.

When it comes to organizing the creative activities of future elementary school teachers, it is appropriate to define what creativity is, and then choose the criteria for organizing creative activities. The concept of "creativity" is considered the analytical basis of many sciences. In determining its meanings, the fact that this ability is brilliant is important. The concept includes such meanings as "creative attitude", "creative activity", "creative work", "creative person", "creative identity". At the end of the 19th century, views on the concept of creativity were put forward by many philosophers, and each of them has its own individuality and variety of thinking. Therefore, creativity is "human activity that creates new material and spiritual values of social importance" "Creativity is one of the forms of human activity aimed at eliminating contradictions, for which objective (social, moral) and subjective personal conditions (knowledge, skills, creative abilities) are necessary, the result of which is innovation and progress.

The heuristic creativity of the teacher means the bold assimilation and promotion of innovations in the professional activity taking place in the world, that is, the formation of ideas, hypotheses based on it, and the consistent realization of their closeness to reality, probability, and reliability. and in this, the ability to act boldly in a new situation, the development of thinking based on the process of thinking is observed.

The creation of new theories of social importance is embodied in the teacher's creativity, he comes up with his own independent ideas and suggestions, which can only be achieved by skilled and experienced teachers.

European sociologists call the positive state of the teacher's work as "feeling the flow", that is, fully engaging in one's work and being satisfied in the process of work, which, in turn, leads to the teacher's high internal testifies to the fact that the reflexive state is strong.

The labor activity of teachers who do not feel creativity and satisfaction from their work in the process of their profession often leads to inactivity, quick exhaustion of nerves and irritability.

Humanity's self-awareness as a subject of creativity has determined new directions for considering the problems and concepts of creativity. Philosophers study the essence of human creative activity, problems of epistemological and general methodological features. Accordingly, in the local philosophy of the 20th century, the goal of trying to solve the problem of "CREATIVE MAN" was leading. For a further substantive description of creative pedagogical activity, it is necessary to refer to the concept of "creativity" - creativity, which is considered the central link of the considered category. One of the developers of the theory of creativity is E. P. Torrens, who defines creativity as the process of emergence of sensitivity to problems, lack of knowledge, their inconsistency, inconsistency; Dj. Gilford distinguishes four factors of creativity on the basis of his model: originality, semantic flexibility, figurative flexibility and semantic spontaneous flexibility in the creative activity of future elementary school teachers. insufficient methodological support for organization; - lack of importance in conducting seminar-training and master classes aimed at developing communicative

competence and assimilation of innovations related to the field, in addition to directing students to creative activities in the educational process; - lack of attention to the formation of knowledge, skills and competences in the effective use of information technologies in the performance of tasks and exercises related to creativity, creation of electronic educational resources, etc. In the book "Teacher's Pedagogical Creativity" by V. I. Zagvyazinsky, creative activity is defined as "creating a new pedagogic system, discovering unknown laws, new ideas, methods, tools; to create new things, to create by awakening the forces based on the inner essence of a person" is defined.

From the scientist's point of view, the following different aspects of the pedagogue's creativity are highlighted:

1. Strictly defined and limited in terms of time. If an unexpected situation occurs in the lesson, the teacher must make a new decision in a short period of time.
2. Since pedagogical creativity is integrally connected with the educational process, it should always bring positive results. Negatives can only be imaginary tests and guesses.
3. Pedagogical creativity is always a collaborative creative work.
4. A significant part of creativity is performed in front of people in a public way (the ability to control one's own mental state).

RESULTS. The following can be included in the objective conditions of difficulties and problems arising in the creative activity of a primary school teacher:

- a) lack of sufficient methodological support;
- b) superficiality in performance evaluation;
- c) involvement in secondary tasks.

The following constitute a series of difficulties arising in connection with the peculiarities of the pedagogue's personality: - insufficient internal strength and capabilities in the implementation of pedagogical activities; - violation of the mechanism of self-direction, which does not allow to change the activity in a coherent way to the reforms in the field; - negative psychological conditions (distrust, nervousness, fear, dissatisfaction with one's work, etc.).

Eliminating the difficulties that arise in the teacher's work requires the following strategies:

- 1) professional development (constructive strategy);
- 2) psychological protection (protection strategy);
- 3) professional deformation (destructive strategy).

Challenges for skilled educators are closely related to overcoming barriers to innovation. Obstacles encountered in pedagogical activity are often manifested in the form of limiting the activities of the pedagogue. It is advisable to use more than one strategy to solve the difficulties that arise in connection with this typology. For example, the difficulties that arise in the work of young teachers, first of all, gradually improving their professional development, providing them with psychological support in solving problematic situations related to professional activity, and establishing a sense of self-confidence and responsibility and requires strategies to successfully navigate changing situations. In the course of the research, the viewpoints of what a creative pedagogue should be are summarized, pedagogical activity involves the creative solution of many practical problems, that is, the ability to anticipate the educational process, design and organize it, diagnose students it was concluded that it is a requirement to obtain and improve their development. For this, the

teacher needs to have skills specific to his profession: to have independence, professional sensitivity and empathy, to be able to think critically, to feel the problem, to anticipate complex situations, to strive to create an individual creative style, and to develop the qualities of self-development. . In a word, creativity is considered as an activity that creates some kind of quality innovation.

DISCUSSION. Creative thinking is the main criterion for creative activity. According to G. Ergasheva, who researched the main components of the development of creative thinking in students, "the spiritual and psychological climate in the team should be directed towards creating a creative environment, and eliminate factors that have a negative effect on creativity. A favorable psychological environment is characterized by the following: an increase in the creative process in all students, freedom from stereotypes, the absence of awkward discussions, initiative and independence, interest and readiness for creative professional activity. Of course, when paying attention to these aspects, it is necessary to focus on the clearly visible characteristics of students, to consider and encourage their individual capabilities. In our opinion, creating an environment of healthy competition among students, giving them the opportunity to compete and test their strength in preparing for the organization of collective creative activities will motivate them to support creative ideas. The result of creativity is manifested not only in the creation of some kind of product, but also in the development of the creative subject itself, that is, in the development of human activities. Creative development, like all development, includes two types of elements: reproductive (restoration of what already exists) and creative (innovation that allows us to move forward). Creative action is divided into several stages, such as the emergence of a problem, preparation for a solution, emergence of an idea, and finally, its embodiment.

CONCLUSION. In our opinion, the basis of a teacher's creativity is his interest in his profession, his internal motivation expressing his interest, the development of the field of will and his desire for radically changed activities. Therefore, it is appropriate to support the actions of the future teacher in the direction of his interests, to set specific goals and tasks for students, and to actively involve them in creative activities.

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